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Title: How should I tell you this? The effects of the image used to convey that a natural yogurt is sweetened on consumer expectations and willingness to buy

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Abstract: This study aimed to assess how packaging imagery used to convey that a natural yogurt is sweetened influences consumer expectations and willingness to buy. Four packages of sweetened natural yogurt were designed, in which the message that they were sweetened was conveyed through three different images (sugar cubes, a sack of sugar and a spoon of sugar) and through only text. The results of a pretest consisting of a word association task and a main experiment consisting of an online survey show that packages in which the message that the yogurt is sweetened is conveyed by using an image together with a textual claim instead of just a textual claim are expected to be sweeter. However, some differences can be appreciated depending on the specific image that is depicted (with the package showing an image of sugar cubes raising the higher sweetness expectations). Moreover, results show that Willingness to buy is positively associated with the attributes Natural Ingredients, Healthy and Quality, and in a slightly negative way with the attribute Sweet. Overall, these results suggest that although using packaging imagery to convey a message may enhance consumer expectations and willingness to buy, its effect on consumers' attitude towards the product may ultimately depend on the subject of the image that is depicted and in the valence of the message to be conveyed. These findings are discussed in the context of packaging design and consumer research, and directions for further research are provided. This study may help packaging designers and dairy companies to better communicate the desired message to consumers and to improve the marketing performance of their products.

1 **Title**

2 2 How should I tell you this? The effects of the image used to convey that a natural yogurt is
3 3 sweetened on consumer expectations and willingness to buy

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18 18 **Declarations of interest:** none.

19 **Abstract**

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21 21 sweetened influences consumer expectations and willingness to buy. Four packages of sweetened
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30 30 attributes Natural Ingredients, Healthy and Quality, and in a slightly negative way with the attribute
31 31 Sweet. Overall, these results suggest that although using packaging imagery to convey a message
32 32 may enhance consumer expectations and willingness to buy, its effect on consumers' attitude
33 33 towards the product may ultimately depend on the subject of the image that is depicted and in the
34 34 valence of the message to be conveyed. These findings are discussed in the context of packaging
35 35 design and consumer research, and directions for further research are provided. This study may help

36 packaging designers and dairy companies to better communicate the desired message to consumers
37 and to improve the marketing performance of their products.

38 **Keywords**

39 packaging imagery; visual cue; verbal cue; expectations; perception; consumer research

40 **Highlights**

- 41 • The effect of packaging imagery on expectations and response is studied.
- 42 • The image used to convey sweetness affects sensory and non-sensory expectations.
- 43 • An image depicting sugar cubes raises the highest sweetness expectations.
- 44 • Depicting a sugar sack enhances naturalness expectations and willingness to buy.
- 45 • Making the concept sweet too salient may enhance unhealthfulness expectations.

46 1. Introduction

1
2 47 Spanish households spend 8.59% of their food budget on dairy products. The fermented milk
3 48 category is the one that has the greatest presence in households, accounting for 38.7% of the sales
4 49 and 15.34 liters per person per year consumption. Within this category, yogurt plays a key role and
5 50 accounts for 65.2% of sales in the category of fermented milk (MAPAMA, 2017). Consumption of
6 51 yogurt and fermented milk is associated with numerous health benefits and both products are among
7 52 the most common fresh dairy products consumed around the world (Donovan & Shamir, 2014).

11 53 In Spain, different types of yogurts are classified as follows: natural yogurts, natural sugar-sweetened
12 54 yogurts, sweetened yogurts, fruit yogurts, juices and/or other foods, flavored yogurts and yogurts
13 55 pasteurized after fermentation (BOE, 2014). Natural sweetened yogurts are those natural yogurts in
14 56 which edible sugar or sugars were added. As far as the energy level is concerned, it means that the
15 57 average of 64 kcal in natural yogurts can reach up to 100 kcal in natural sweetened yogurts (data per
16 58 100 grams, BEDCA, 2018). The advantage of natural sweetened yogurts is that consumers do not
17 59 need any additional products (sugar or other natural or artificial sweeteners) to eat it with. Roughly
18 60 50% of people add sugar to natural yogurts before eating them and some studies have shown that
19 61 the average amount of sugar (or other sweeteners, such as honey or jam) added to natural yogurts is
20 62 above the average amount of sugar that natural sweetened yogurts contain (measured in sucrose,
21 63 Saint-Eve et al., 2016).

28 64 Due to its intrinsic characteristics, such as its creamy texture and its rapid degradation, sweetened
29 65 yogurt is always marketed packed. Yet, research has shown that the functions of food packaging go
30 66 well beyond the protection and handling of the product given that packaging has the ability to grab
31 67 consumer attention and to influence consumer expectations and response (Rundh, 2005, 2009,
32 68 2013). Indeed, literature shows that consumer perception and attitude may be affected by physical
33 69 packaging cues such as its shape (Becker, van Rompay, Schifferstein, & Galetzka, 2011; Rebollar,
34 70 Lidón, Serrano, Martín, & Fernández, 2012; Velasco, Woods, Petit, Cheok, & Spence, 2016) or its
35 71 weight (Piqueras-Fiszman & Spence, 2012), and by visual cues such as its material (Magnier &
36 72 Schoormans, 2017; Rebollar et al., 2017), its color (Piqueras-Fiszman & Spence, 2015; Spence,
37 73 2018) or even the typography used in the label texts (Celhay, Boisselle, & Cohen, 2015; Velasco,
38 74 Salgado-Montejo, Marmolejo-Ramos, & Spence, 2014).

45 75 Nevertheless, despite being one of the most common food packaging design elements and a
46 76 prominent visual cue (Underwood & Klein, 2002), the effect of packaging imagery on consumer
47 77 expectations and response has attracted modest scientific attention thus far (for a historical account
48 78 on the topic see Hine, 1995; for more recent reviews, see Piqueras-Fiszman & Spence, 2015, pp.
49 79 173-174; and Simmonds & Spence, 2017, pp. 343-344). Given that packaging is a key
50 80 communication tool between producers and consumers (Celhay & Remaud, 2018; Festila &
51 81 Chrysochou, 2018), one of the main objectives of the images shown on food packaging is to convey
52 82 information (Ares et al., 2011; Underwood & Klein, 2002). Consumers infer meaning from the images
53 83 that appear on packages and consequently use them to identify and categorize products, as well as
54 84 to generate expectations regarding their attributes (Loken, 2006): for example, Rebollar et al. (2016)
55 85 showed that the product that is depicted together with the fresh cheese in the image on the package

1 86 influences the expectations that consumers have about the characteristics of that same fresh
2 87 cheese. Thus, images are commonly used by packaging designers to convey information, and they
3 88 are, together with verbal cues, the most frequently used cues for this purpose (Kauppinen-Räsänen,
4 89 Owusu, & Abeeku Bamfo, 2012; Machiels & Karnal, 2016; Piqueras-Fiszman, Ares, & Varela, 2011).

5
6 90 However, it should be noted that this communication process may rely on different layers of
7 91 information as designers often have to convey several messages to consumers, for which designers
8 92 can use different packaging cues (Ares et al., 2011; Laing & Masoodian, 2016; see also Matthews,
9 93 Simmonds, & Spence, 2019). Among all the possible cues, the most appropriate ones will be those
10 94 that correctly convey the desired message and at the same time have a more positive impact on
11 95 consumers' response. For example, in the case of a sweetened natural yogurt, the designer must
12 96 clearly communicate the product category (i.e. natural yogurt) and the product subcategory (i.e.
13 97 sweetened): in this case, it is reasonable to wonder what kind of cue will be the most adequate for
14 98 each message. Previous studies analyzed the consequences of using one or another kind of cue in
15 99 order to convey the product category (Bone & France, 2001; Rebollar et al., 2017; Underwood &
16 100 Klein, 2002) and even suggested that the packaging shape can be used for that purpose (Arboleda &
17 101 Arce-Lopera, 2015; Velasco et al., 2016). However, it is not clear which kind of cue (i.e. whether
18 102 visual or verbal) is the most adequate to communicate specific product attributes (e.g. that a natural
19 103 yogurt is sweetened) and how this decision may influence consumer expectations and willingness to
20 104 buy. In contrast to verbal cues, images more easily attract consumer attention at the point of sale
21 105 (Honea & Horsky, 2012; Venter, van der Merwe, de Beer, Kempen, & Bosman, 2011) and require a
22 106 lower level of cognitive effort, as they are processed in a more unintentional and unconscious way
23 107 (Mueller, Lockshin, & Louviere, 2009; Underwood & Klein, 2002). As a consequence, consumers
24 108 generate expectations more quickly by looking at an image than by reading a text (Underwood &
25 109 Klein, 2002). Indeed, some authors suggest that conveying a given concept through imagery helps to
26 110 make it more accessible in consumers' mind (Gil-Pérez, Rebollar, Lidón, Martín, et al., 2019; Gil-
27 111 Pérez, Rebollar, Lidón, Piqueras-Fiszman, & van Trijp, 2019), thus making it more salient and
28 112 thereby affecting perception (Adams, Hart, Gilmer, Lloyd-Richardson, & Burton, 2014; Rebollar et al.,
29 113 2017). Given that salience is considered to play a key role in the process of shaping expectations
30 114 (Piqueras-Fiszman & Spence, 2015), we hypothesize:

31 115 H1. Packages conveying that a yogurt has been sweetened by depicting an image together
32 116 with a textual claim (rather than just by a textual claim) will increase (decrease) sweetness
33 117 expectations.

34 118 Moreover, the question arises of what the differences would be depending on the specific image
35 119 selected as visual cue. Findings of previous investigations on the manipulation of the main image
36 120 that is shown on the package show that what is depicted may make an impact on consumer
37 121 expectations and response (Machiels & Karnal, 2016; Mizutani et al., 2010). Therefore, it seems
38 122 reasonable to wonder not only about the effect of using an image to convey a message like that a
39 123 natural yogurt is sweetened, but also about the effect of the specific image used for that purpose.
40 124 Manipulating packaging imagery may elicit different meanings (e.g. enhancing a particular concept,
41 125 Gil-Pérez, Rebollar, Lidón, Martín, et al., 2019; Gil-Pérez, Rebollar, Lidón, Piqueras-Fiszman, & van
42 126 Trijp, 2019) and anchor consumer judgement (e.g. making consumers think that the number of

127 product units depicted in the package correlates to the amount of product contained within it,
128 Madzharov & Block, 2010), thus influencing consumer expectations and behavior (Neyens et al.,
129 2015). Based on the above, we propose:

130 H2a. Packages displaying images depicting a high (low) amount of sugar will increase
131 (decrease) sweetness expectations.

132 H2b. Packages displaying images depicting a high (low) level of naturalness will increase
133 (decrease) the expectation of natural ingredients having been used in the production of the
134 yogurt.

135 In addition, it should be noted that consumers are gradually becoming more health conscious
136 (Anesbury, Nguyen, & Bogomolova, 2018; Grunert & Wills, 2007) and, thus, sugar consumption and
137 sweet products are being increasingly associated with poor dietary choices (Lustig, Schmidt, &
138 Brindis, 2012; Sütterlin & Siegrist, 2015). In contrast, a growing market trend shows that consumers
139 tend to prefer natural and unprocessed foods (Fernqvist & Ekelund, 2014; Román, Sánchez-Siles, &
140 Siegrist, 2017; Smith, Barratt, & Selsøe Sørensen, 2015), which tend to be considered healthier and
141 of better quality (Machiels & Karnal, 2016; Román et al., 2017). Accordingly, we propose:

142 H3a. Expected sweetness will be negatively associated to healthfulness expectations and to
143 willingness to buy.

144 H3b. Expected naturalness will be positively associated to healthfulness and quality
145 expectations, and to willingness to buy.

146 **2. Materials and methods**

147 In order to test the proposed hypotheses, a pretest and a main experiment were conducted. The
148 pretest aimed to assess whether the image used to convey that the yogurt is sweetened affects the
149 attributes that the consumers associate with the product, with a particular interest in the mental
150 associations regarding the product sweetness. To that end, a word association task was conducted
151 using four different packages of natural sweetened yogurt designed *ad hoc* for this study. The main
152 experiment aimed to analyze whether the image used to convey that the yogurt is sweetened affects
153 consumer expectations and willingness to buy, and consisted of an online survey. In it, participants
154 were asked to evaluate their expectations and their willingness to buy in relation to the same stimuli
155 used in the first experiment. Taken together, the pretest and the main experiment aimed to offer
156 different and complementary insights into how using imagery to convey a message affects consumer
157 perception and response.

158 **2.1. Stimuli**

159 A market study was carried out prior to the design of the stimuli to become familiar with the most
160 frequent characteristics of the packages of sweetened natural yogurt sold in the Spanish market. It
161 entailed a series of supermarket visits in which 29 sweetened natural yogurts from a total of 12
162 brands were analyzed. The results showed that the most frequently depicted subjects used to convey
163 sweetness were sugar cubes (N=7, 24.1%), a sugar sack (N=6, 20.7%), and a spoon with sugar

164 (N=3, 10.3%), while the remaining packages relied on textual cues and did not use images to convey
165 sweetness (N=13, 44.8%). According to these findings, four kinds of stimuli were designed in a way
166 they would resemble the appearance any of these products might have on the market. Each package
167 included the same elements: the words “Yogur Natural Azucarado” (sweetened natural yoghurt, in
168 English), an image of a cow, the brand (Yulé – created specifically for this investigation so that the
169 participants could not deduce certain attributes of the products based on their prior experiences with
170 other brands), the nutrition information and other symbols (e.g., barcode, recycled package). The
171 only difference between packages was the image shown to indicate that the yogurt was sweetened.

172 The images used were the ones more commonly seen in these kinds of yogurt packages: sugar
173 cubes, a spoon of sugar, a sack of sugar and no image. These stimuli will be hereafter referred to,
174 respectively, as *Sugar cubes*, *Sugar sack*, *Sugar spoon* and *Only text*. According to our hypotheses,
175 two stimuli were intended to depict a large amount of sugar (*Sugar cubes* and *Sugar sack*) and one
176 stimulus was intended to depict a high level of naturalness (*Sugar sack*). In order to verify the
177 adequacy of the images that were chosen to represent each case, a manipulation check was
178 conducted. Fifty-one people (28 female, 23 male; mean age of 24.9 years; standard deviation of 7.9
179 years) were asked to rate, according to a Likert scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree),
180 how much sugar did they consider was depicted in each image, and how related to the concept
181 ‘natural’ each image was. The results of a one-way repeated measures analysis of variance (within-
182 subjects ANOVA; Table 1) showed that, as it was intended, the *Sugar sack* and the *Sugar cubes*
183 images were considered to depict a larger amount of sugar than the *Sugar spoon* image, and that the
184 *Sugar sack* image was judged as being more related to the concept ‘natural’ than the *Sugar cubes*
185 and the *Sugar spoon* images.

[Insert Table 1 around here]

187 Once the adequacy of the chosen imagery had been checked, the final stimuli were designed. The
188 visual stimuli used in the experiments (Fig. 1) were photorealistic renderings created using
189 Photoshop CS5 (Adobe Systems Inc., San Jose, CA, U.S.A.) and Keyshot 4 (Luxion Inc., Tustin, CA,
190 U.S.A.).

[Insert Figure 1 around here]

192 2.2. Pretest (word association)

193 The pretest aimed to explore whether the image used to convey that the yogurt has been sweetened
194 affects the accessibility of the concept ‘Sweet’. To that end, a word association task was conducted.
195 Word association is a qualitative research technique usually used in sociology and psychology
196 (Schmitt, 1998). This technique is based on free answers given by the participant as a response to a
197 stimulus; these answers provide a better understanding of the mental representation that consumers
198 have of the stimulus in question. When this technique is applied to food, the answers given make it
199 possible to identify the most relevant concepts for consumer’s buying decisions (Roininen, Arvola, &
200 Lähteenmäki, 2006).

1 201 A convenience sample of 112 people (62 female, 50 male) participated in this pretest, all residing in
2 202 Spain. Their mean age was 33.5 years with a standard deviation of 13.5 years. Participants were
3 203 recruited both from mailing lists and by approaching them at the university campus, were not
4 204 compensated for participating, and carried out the task on a voluntary and anonymous basis. The
5 205 experiment was conducted in a quiet room with stable and homogeneous conditions of light and
6 206 temperature in the School of Engineering and Architecture of Zaragoza University. The participants
7 207 were randomly divided into four groups of 28 people. No statistically relevant difference was found in
8 208 the composition of groups regarding age and gender.

11 209 Each group of participants performed a task with one of the four stimuli shown in the Figure 1.
12 210 Participants were asked to evaluate the stimuli and to write down the first three words, associations,
13 211 thoughts or feelings that came to their minds. The stimuli were shown on a 23" LED monitor with a
14 212 resolution of 1920 x 1080px and a refresh rate of 60Hz and were of a similar size to the real-life
15 213 package. There was no time limitation to perform the task and participants could write one, two or
16 214 three ideas.

21 215 2.3. Main experiment (online survey)

23 216 The main experiment aimed to assess whether the image used to convey sweetness affects
24 217 consumer expectations and willingness to buy, thus addressing H1, H2 and H3. Participants were
25 218 recruited from mailing lists and social media, and by posting a link to the survey on University
26 219 webpages. They were not compensated for participating, and carried out the survey on a voluntary
27 220 and anonymous basis, using an online survey data collection tool: SurveyMonkey™. Participants
28 221 were not given a time limit to complete the survey or any particular section thereof. They were shown
29 222 photorealistic renderings (Fig. 1) and given a questionnaire to evaluate them. A within-subject
30 223 experimental design was used, so all survey participants saw the same packages. The packages
31 224 were shown one at a time and in a randomized order.

32 225 One hundred and fifty-seven people (95 female, 63 male) other than those who took part in the
33 226 pretest participated in this investigation, all residing in Spain. Their mean age was 29.1 years with a
34 227 standard deviation of 10.1 years.

35 228 The survey was divided into two sections: demographic information of the participants (age and
36 229 gender) and the presentation of the packages to analyze—the visual stimuli in Figure 1. For each
37 230 package, the survey evaluated a total of four product attributes which were selected for being seen
38 231 as particularly relevant in case of natural sweetened yogurts: one sensory attribute (Sweet) and three
39 232 non-sensory attributes (Healthy, Natural Ingredients, and Quality).

40 233 Participants were asked to evaluate the four product attributes for each of the four packages
41 234 according to a Likert scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). Willingness to buy was
42 235 evaluated using the same Likert scale of 1 (would not buy under any circumstances) to 7 (would be
43 236 definitely willing to buy). It was specified that all the packages contained the same type of product
44 237 (i.e., sweetened natural yogurt), the same quantity of yogurt and had the same cost (though the price
45 238 was not specified).

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239 2.4. Statistical Analyses

240 2.4.1. Pretest (word association)

241 All word associations made by the participants were analyzed qualitatively. The terms with similar
242 meaning were grouped using inter-rater consensus technique (Armstrong, Gosling, Weinman, &
243 Martaeu, 1997; Glaser & Strauss, 1967). Each researcher individually evaluated the results and,
244 consequently, the classification of the final categories was agreed on by three raters. This
245 triangulation technique has been used by other authors dealing with qualitative techniques (Guerrero
246 et al., 2010). Only those categories that were mentioned by at least five participants were taken into
247 consideration (Piqueras-Fizman, Velasco, Salgado-Montejo, & Spence, 2013).

248 HJ-Biplot (Galindo, 1986) was used to analyze the word association task. This exploratory technique
249 is a variant of the biplot methods proposed by Gabriel (1971). The biplot methods make it possible to
250 plot the rows (stimuli) and columns (words) of the data matrix as points on a low dimension vector
251 space. The interpretation of this method is similar to other multivariate techniques. The distances
252 between row markers are interpreted as an inverse function of similarities, so closer markers (stimuli)
253 are more similar. The cosines of the angles between the column vectors (words) approximate the
254 correlation between variables in such a way that small acute angles are associated with high positive
255 correlations, obtuse angles are associated with negative correlations and right angles are associated
256 with uncorrelated variables. In the same way, the cosines of angles between the column markers
257 (words) and the axes approximate the correlations between them. Besides, the order of the
258 orthogonal projections of the row markers (stimuli) onto column markers (words) approximates the
259 order of the row values in that column of the data matrix. Thus, this technique allows to analyze the
260 similarity (or dissimilarity) between stimuli in relation to the latent variables defined by the word
261 categories. The data was processed and analyzed using MULTBILOT (Vicente-Villardón, 2015).

262 2.4.2. Main experiment (online survey)

263 A one-way repeated measures analysis of variance (within-subjects ANOVA) was used to analyze
264 the statistical differences between stimuli for each individual attribute, in order to assess the effect of
265 the image manipulation on consumer expectations and willingness to buy. For the comparisons of
266 pairs following the analysis of variance, the Bonferroni correction was used.

267 In addition, the Individual Differences Model (Carroll & Chang, 1970; Horan, 1969) was used to
268 analyze the perception structure of the individuals in the ordering of the stimuli based on a small set
269 of dimensions defined by the attributes. This technique is included within multidimensional scaling
270 techniques and has been used primarily to characterize variation in judged stimulus structure across
271 individuals. It allows both to study how each stimulus relates to each dependent variable (i.e. each of
272 the measured expectations and the willingness to buy), and to assess how each dependent variable
273 relates to each other (thus showing the perception structure of the individuals).

274 This method is also known as INDSCAL. In this study, a matrix (4X4) of similarities between
275 packages was calculated for each individual. These similarities were obtained from each individual
276 score given to the different packages of yogurts in relation to their attributes. This technique allows

277 the creation of a space of consensus for the individuals showing the similarities between the
1 278 packages of yogurts. In addition, it is possible to find out the weights that each individual gave to the
2 279 dimensions obtained in the consensus space. The weights reflect the importance that the individuals
3 280 associate to the dimensions in the stimuli space. Although one person can perceive one of the
4 281 dimensions to be more important than the other, another person can have the opposite perception.
5 282 This technique was used to evaluate the attributes, as well as willingness to buy. The analysis was
6 283 conducted using the PROXCAL algorithm (Leeuw & Heiser, 1980), and Euclidian distance was used
7 284 as a measure of similarity. The criterion to choose the number of dimensions in the consensus space
8 285 was based on goodness of fit and the number of stimuli included in the analysis. S-Stress was used
9 286 to determine goodness of fit. If this measurement is low, it indicates that the configuration obtained in
10 287 the map (or space) is good. Kruskal and Wish (1984) deemed the solution to be acceptable when the
11 288 S-Stress values are less than 0.1.

18 289 Moreover, the vector model (Schiffman, Reynolds, & Young, 1981) was used to interpret the
19 290 dimensions of preference in accordance with the observable attributes. This procedure uses the
20 291 multiple-regression technique to determine the direction of the attributes. The means of the individual
21 292 scores of attributes are used to calculate the multiple regression, and the standardized regression
22 293 coefficients (β_1 ; β_2 ; β_3) are computed and drawn as coordinates in the three-dimensional
23 294 stimulus space. Finally, a line is drawn through the origin of the stimulus consensus space and
24 295 through coordinates defined by the regression coefficients. This model helps to interpret the
25 296 dimensions of the space of similarities using the attributes forming the similarities between the
26 297 stimuli. Moreover, the attribute-vector is shown as a line in the space representing packages of
27 298 yogurts in which the projection of each stimulus corresponds to the level of attributes possessed by
28 299 that stimulus. If the attribute in question is strongly related with the stimuli space, then the projections
30 300 of the stimuli will coincide very closely with the value of the attribute and the correlation between the
31 301 projection and the attribute will be quite high. When two attributes are facing in the same direction,
32 302 this also indicates a high correlation. When the points that represent the vector are close to a
33 303 dimension and far from the center, it means they are relevant for explaining that dimension. If an
34 304 attribute is in a position halfway between two dimensions, it indicates that the attribute is explained in
35 305 both dimensions. If a vector-attribute is close to the center of the stimuli space, it means that it is
36 306 insignificant in the explanation of the dimensions of that space.

37 307 This model allowed the packages to be ordered according to each of the attributes evaluated by the
38 308 subjects, also making it possible to determine which attributes had a high correlation in the stimuli
39 309 evaluation. Subjects' willingness to buy was included as an external value to explore the dimension
40 310 with the highest correlation. SPSS Statistics 23 (Armonk, NY, U.S.A.) was used for data analysis and
41 311 processing.

52 312 **3. Results**

53 313 3.1. Pretest (word association)

54 314 The elicited words were clustered into eight categories, corresponding to those mentioned by more
55 315 than five participants (Piqueras-Fiszman et al., 2013). The most mentioned associations were
56 316 concepts related to 'Sweet', 'Natural yogurt', and 'Nature' (Table 2). In addition, the data was also

317 processed in the form of a biplot graph (Fig. 2). The first two axes of the HJ-Biplot analysis explained
318 89.22% of the data variability. Axis 1 was mainly defined by the term 'Healthy' against 'Sweet'. This
319 axis separated *Sugar cubes* and *Sugar sack* stimuli (more frequently associated with 'Sweet') from
320 *Sugar spoon* and *Only text* stimuli (more frequently associated with 'Healthy'). Axis 2 was defined by
321 the terms 'Yogurt' and 'Nature' against the term 'Fresh'. This axis separated *Sugar sack* stimulus
322 against *Sugar cubes* and *Only text*, whereas *Sugar spoon* stimulus occupied the intermediate
323 position.

324 [Insert Table 2 around here]

325 [Insert Figure 2 around here]

326 Overall, these results seem to support the notion that conveying sweetness by using an image
327 together with a textual claim (instead of just a textual claim) may influence sweetness expectations.
328 Specifically, the results suggest that imagery helps to enhance the salience of the depicted concepts,
329 since the stimuli depicting images designed to convey sweetness (namely, *Sugar cubes*, *Sugar*
330 *spoon* and *Sugar sack*) appear to have favored the elicitation of concepts related to 'Sweet'
331 (compared to the *Only text* stimulus). In addition, the pretest results also suggest that this effect may
332 depend on the specific image used to convey sweetness, since apparently relevant differences may
333 be seen in the frequency of elicitation of concepts related to 'Sweet' that were mentioned by the
334 participants for each stimulus (with the *Sugar cubes* and the *Sugar sack* images seeming to have
335 favored the accessibility of the concept 'Sweet' compared to that of the *Sugar spoon* image). Finally,
336 the biplot graph also seem to show a tendency by which the stronger the association that a stimulus
337 raises to concepts related to sweetness, the weaker the association that the same stimulus raises to
338 concepts related to healthfulness.

339 3.2. Main experiment (online survey)

340 All the results obtained using the variance technique analysis gave statistically significant values
341 regarding both the four attributes tested and the willingness to buy the product (Table 3, Fig. 3).

342 The results seem to be aligned with the findings of the pretest, since the greatest difference in the
343 results can be seen in relation to the Sweet attribute. In fact, the packages conveying sweetness
344 through an image and a textual claim (*Sugar sack*, *Sugar cubes* and *Sugar spoon*) raised higher
345 sweetness expectations than the package conveying sweetness only through a textual claim (*Only*
346 *text*), supporting H1. In addition, regarding the Sweet attribute, there was a significant difference
347 between the *Sugar cubes* package in relation to the others, with the *Sugar cubes* package obtaining
348 the highest mean value ($\bar{X}=5.47$, $SD=1.47$) and the *Only text* package obtaining the lowest mean
349 value ($\bar{X}=4.48$, $SD=1.56$). This partially supports H2a, since although the *Sugar cubes* package
350 depicts a high amount of sugar, it is also the case of the *Sugar sack* package and yet it raised similar
351 sweetness expectations than the *Sugar spoon* package ($\bar{X}=5.09$, $SD=1.46$ and $\bar{X}=5.03$, $SD=1.34$,
352 respectively). Regarding the Natural Ingredients attribute, the *Sugar sack* package raised the highest
353 naturalness expectations ($\bar{X}=4.22$, $SD=1.59$), supporting H2b. In addition, the results relating to the
354 other non-sensory attributes (namely, Healthy and Quality) also had a significant difference between
355 their extreme values. Indeed, all the attributes (except Sweet) obtained structurally similar results,

with the *Sugar sack* stimulus obtaining the highest results and the *Sugar cubes* package obtaining the lowest results. The results for Willingness to buy also followed a similar pattern, showing that the package obtaining the highest value was the one depicting a sugar sack ($\bar{X}=4.48$, $SD=1.64$), and the one with the lowest value was the one depicting the sugar cubes ($\bar{X}=3.97$, $SD=1.69$).

[Insert Table 3 around here]

[Insert Figure 3 around here]

Regarding the multidimensional analysis results, the consensus space showed similarities between the stimuli (Fig. 4). The dimensionality chosen for the multidimensional scaling solution was that of three dimensions (S-Stress = 0.00233). The reason by which three and not two dimensions were chosen was that the S-Stress obtained by using two dimensions was close to 0.1 and the *Sugar sack* stimulus was not represented accurately in a two-dimensional space. Thus, the first dimension differentiated the *Sugar cubes* package from the *Only text* package, the second dimension differentiated the *Sugar sack* package from the rest of the packages, and the third dimension differentiated the *Sugar spoon* package from the *Sugar cubes* package. Analysis of the layout of the packages regarding the attributes showed that the attributes Sweet and Healthy were closely associated with Dimension I. The attributes Natural Ingredients and Willingness to buy were closely associated with the Dimension II and the attribute Quality was equally associated with Dimensions II and III. In the analysis of individuals' weights, 72% gave similar importance to dimensions I, II and III, compared to 15% who gave most importance to dimension I and to 12% who gave more importance to dimension II. Just 1% of individuals rated only dimension III.

The multidimensional analysis results support H3 since it can be seen how Willingness to Buy had a strong positive connection with the attributes Natural Ingredients, Healthy, and Quality; and how, on the other hand, the attribute Sweet displayed a strong negative connection with the attribute Healthy and a weak negative connection with Willingness to buy.

[Insert Figure 4 around here]

4. Discussion

This study aimed to analyze whether the images used on packaging to convey that a yogurt is sweetened make an impact on consumer expectations and on willingness to buy. The results of the current research enrich the literature on how the product extrinsic cues influence consumer expectations and response by showing that the image chosen to convey the message that the yogurt is sweetened influences both consumer sensory and non-sensory expectations and that it also affects willingness to buy. These findings enhance our understanding of the effects of conveying a message on food packaging (in this case, indicating that yogurt is sweetened) through different cues, thus helping both designers and producers to design clearer and more effective packages for their products.

391 4.1. Contributions

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2 392 The results of this study show that the package that has only text and no images raises the lowest
3 393 sweetness expectations. This finding contributes to the literature by supporting previous research
4 394 which suggest that visual information is more powerful than verbal information (McQuarrie & Mick,
5 395 2003; McQuarrie & Phillips, 2005), and is in accordance with the findings by Rebollar et al. (2017)
6 396 that suggested that using a visual cue to convey a secondary message in a food package enhances
7 397 consumer expectations. Overall, literature suggests that salience plays a key role in the process of
8 398 shaping expectations (Piqueras-Fiszman & Spence, 2015), since increasing the salience of a given
9 399 concept leads to an increased activation of the parts of the brain devoted to processing it (González
10 400 et al., 2006). Compared to texts, images are considered to increase the salience of the conveyed
11 401 message because they more easily attract attention and are processed more quickly (Honea &
12 402 Horsky, 2012; Sehrwet & Kundu, 2007; Smith et al., 2015; Venter et al., 2011). Thus, the results of
13 403 this study support the notion that conveying a message through imagery helps to enhance the
14 404 salience of the depicted concepts, since consumers expected a yogurt contained in a package
15 405 showing sugar-related images to be sweeter than a yogurt displaying only textual claims. In addition,
16 406 the results of the word association conducted in this study also seem to be aligned with this notion,
17 407 since the package that used only text to convey sweetness (i.e., the package without an image
18 408 related to sweetness) elicited the lowest number of terms related to the concept 'Sweet'.

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27 409 Moreover, these results contribute to the literature by demonstrating that the specific image chosen
28 410 to be depicted in packaging imagery does make an impact on consumer's sensory expectations, thus
29 411 supporting previous research in the field (e.g. Machiels & Karnal, 2016; Mizutani et al., 2010;
30 412 Rebollar et al., 2016). Specifically, in this study, packages with an image of sugar cubes raised
31 413 higher sweetness expectations than packages depicting an image of a sugar spoon or that of a sugar
32 414 sack. Literature devoted to the effect of packaging imagery on consumer expectations and response
33 415 offers a possible explanation to this effect, as it shows that pictures activate information related to the
34 416 immediate visual properties of the product that is depicted, thereby making it and its attributes more
35 417 accessible in consumers' mind (Gil-Pérez, Rebollar, Lidón, Martín, et al., 2019; Madzharov & Block,
36 418 2010; Smith et al., 2015). In this vein, as we hypothesized, on the one hand it can be argued that the
37 419 *Sugar cubes* and the *Sugar sack* images depict a larger sugar amount than the *Sugar spoon* image.
38 420 Thus, a heuristic judgement may be triggered by which consumers infer that the larger the amount of
39 421 sugar depicted in the image, the higher the quantity of sugar present in the product. That would
40 422 support the results of Madzharov and Block (2010), who showed that the number of product units
41 423 (e.g., number of cookies) displayed on the package influences consumers' perceptions of the
42 424 quantity of product (the more cookies are depicted in the package, the more cookies consumers think
43 425 there are contained within). However, on the other hand, these results suggest that other
44 426 mechanisms may be at play, since the *Sugar sack* image also depicts a high amount of sugar and
45 427 yet it raises lower sweetness expectations than the *Sugar cubes* image. In this regard, it should be
46 428 noted that processing fluency literature suggest that when consumers' mental representation of a
47 429 target matches the way the target is presented, this fit increases processing fluency (Chae & Hoegg,
48 430 2013) and increases the accessibility of the depicted concept (González et al., 2006). Thus, both the
49 431 *Sugar cubes* and the *Sugar spoon* images may fit better with consumers' mental representation of

1 432 adding sugar to a product than the *Sugar sack* image, since they accurately represent the way in
2 433 which consumers are used to do that task. From a semiotic point of view, the sign would be
3 434 congruent with the product in which it is applied and it thus would allow to easily access the concept
4 435 of sweet in the consumer's mind (Ares et al., 2011; Lynott & Connell, 2010; Smith et al., 2015). In
5 436 contrast, a sack of sugar would be an element that consumers would not associate with the action of
6 437 adding sugar to products since it would not fit into their everyday experience. Thus, according to our
7 438 results, we propose that the package with an image depicting sugar cubes is the one raising the
8 439 higher sweetness expectations for two reasons. First, because it both depicts a large amount of
9 440 sugar; and second, because it fits into consumers' mental representation of adding sugar to a yogurt.
10 441 In contrast, the other two stimuli (i.e., that of a sugar sack and that of a sugar spoon) only meet one
11 442 of these two criteria each. This is in line with Sperber and Wilson's relevance theory (1995), since
12 443 consumers seem to interpret each image by assuming that each of its features (e.g., the depicted
13 444 quantity of sugar) is situationally relevant (Smith et al., 2015). However, these mechanisms should
14 445 be further tested in order to yield a comprehensive process model and thus empirically test their
15 446 validity.

16 447 As for the effects of the images on naturalness expectations, the results show that the image of a
17 448 sack of sugar raises more naturalness expectations than the rest of the images. According to
18 449 previous research, that could be explained due to the sack serving as a sign that triggers
19 450 associations with concepts related to a natural environment (Chae & Hoegg, 2013; Smith et al.,
20 451 2015). This assumption lines up with earlier studies which suggest that stereotypical information
21 452 associated with food shapes perception (Brierley & Elliott, 2015), and may be explained within a
22 453 semiotic approach (Celhay & Remaud, 2018). In contrast, consumers would not associate nor the
23 454 image of the sugar cubes nor the image of the sugar spoon with the concept of natural ingredients
24 455 because neither of the two images would be easily associated with concepts related to nature, as in
25 456 both cases the sugar is depicted processed and ready for consumption. Thus, this study adds to
26 457 previous research by suggesting that consumers tend to project the attributes of the products
27 458 depicted in the packaging imagery (in this case, naturalness) into the main product, thus modulating
28 459 consumer expectations (Machiels & Karnal, 2016; Rebollar et al., 2016).

29 460 In addition, these results suggest that sweetness expectations are somewhat negatively related to
30 461 healthfulness expectations and to willingness to buy: although the results of the multidimensional
31 462 scaling show that willingness to buy does not have a strong association with the expectations of
32 463 sweetness, a certain negative trend can be seen. Moreover, the biplot pretest results show a strong
33 464 negative association between the number of times that participants elicited words related to the
34 465 concepts 'Sweet' and 'Healthy'. Both findings are in line with our hypotheses and are aligned with a
35 466 growing body of literature that links sugar consumption with an increased risk of a variety of chronic
36 467 diseases (Billich et al., 2018; Lustig et al., 2012). Additionally, the results show that the attribute
37 468 Natural Ingredients has a positive correlation with the attributes Quality and Healthy, which supports
38 469 previous research that suggest that consumers judge products as healthier and of a higher quality
39 470 when they have a high proportion of natural ingredients (Machiels & Karnal, 2016; Román et al.,
40 471 2017; Sütterlin & Siegrist, 2015). In turn, the results show that high naturalness expectations are
41 472 positively related to quality expectations and to willingness to buy, which supports previous literature

473 that suggests that there is a strong positive association link between willingness to buy and such
1 474 attributes as Natural Ingredients, Healthy, and Quality (Fernqvist & Ekelund, 2014; Román et al.,
2 475 2017). This might imply that the higher consumer expectations are of whether the product is natural,
3 476 and/or is made with natural ingredients, the higher their willingness to buy is (Machiels & Karnal,
4 477 2016; Román et al., 2017).

478 Overall, these results support previous work that suggests that packaging imagery has the ability to
8 479 improve consumer attitude towards the product (Underwood & Klein, 2002), since showing the image
9 480 of a sugar sack in the yogurt package enhanced the participants' willingness to buy the product.
10 481 However, it may be noted that this may not always be the case as this effect did not occur for the
11 482 other images. Our results even suggest that the willingness to buy the package displaying an image
12 483 of sugar cubes appear to be even lower than that of the package displaying only a textual claim (i.e.
13 484 with no sugar-related image; see also Rebollar et al., 2016). Literature shows that conveying a
14 485 message by means of an image makes it more salient than doing so through a text because it
15 486 captures attention more quickly and is processed sooner (Honea & Horsky, 2012; Underwood &
16 487 Klein, 2002; Venter et al., 2011), so it seems reasonable to think that consumers' attitude towards a
17 488 product may not only be influenced by the implicit valence of the image depicted in its package (as it
18 489 was shown by Mizutani et al., 2010), but also by the valence of the message to be conveyed. Such a
19 490 'halo effect' occurs when consumers correlate the assessments of different product attributes,
20 491 generalizing positive (or negative) perceptions elicited by a given attribute (Lähteenmäki et al., 2010).
21 492 For example, Rebollar et al. (2017) reported a positive 'halo effect' by which conveying a positive
22 493 message through an image rather than by a textual claim (in their case, that the chips contained in a
23 494 bag of chips had been fried in olive oil) enhanced willingness to buy and consumer expectations for
24 495 all the assessed attributes. In contrast, if the message to be conveyed is not clearly rendered as
25 496 positive by consumers (like it could be the case of this study, where the salience of the 'sweet'
26 497 concept raised by the *Sugar cubes* image may trigger negative mental associations in the mind of
27 498 some consumers; Billich et al., 2018; Lustig et al., 2012), providing too much relevance to it by
28 499 means of a visual cue may end up being counterproductive and detrimental to consumer
30 500 expectations and willingness to buy (resulting in a negative 'halo effect'). However, further research
31 501 is needed in order to assess the validity of these hypotheses and to better understanding the effect of
32 502 packaging imagery in consumer attitude and product acceptance.

503 4.2. Limitations and future research

504 Regarding the limitations of this research, it should be noted that the results obtained may have been
505 influenced by visual factors that have not been taken into account, such as the size of the image or
506 the aesthetics of the composition. As for the visual design, the use of graphic elements such as
507 images of the cow or a natural environment may have biased the results increasing the accessibility
508 to some concepts over others, but since they were shown in all the stimuli, their possible effects were
509 thus cancelled. Moreover, part of this study was conducted using an online survey on social media
510 meaning that the participants therein came only from that environment. Additionally, the number of
511 participants who carried out the word association task was modest. Consequently, there are
512 limitations regarding the participants' diversity and characteristics. It would be interesting to carry out

1 513 further testing to see if the obtained results can be extrapolated to other countries, since all the
2 514 participants were Spanish.

3 515 Although we propose that the differences between the sweetness expectations raised by the images
4 516 can be partly explained by how well the images fit with consumers' mental representation of the
5 517 action of adding sugar to a yogurt, this would need to further be tested and other alternative
6 518 explanations should not be ruled out. In addition, one should be cautious when drawing conclusions
7 519 regarding the causal relation of some of the effects reported in this study. While it may be tempting to
8 520 think that the higher accessibility to the 'Sweet' concept given by the images depicting a large
9 521 amount of sugar explains the higher sweetness expectations elicited by those images, this kind of
10 522 causal link has not been explicitly assessed in this study. Thus, further research is advised in order to
11 523 understand how the results of the word association task conducted in the pretest may relate to the
12 524 images' effect on consumer expectations.

13 525 Furthermore, it is worth noting that consumers' willingness to buy has been measured by means of a
14 526 hypothetical context set in an online survey. This may raise some concern about these results truly
15 527 reflecting consumers' demand and not only consumers' product acceptability, since the behavior of
16 528 consumers in the field might be different from the one expected based on the presented results
17 529 (Elbakidze & Nayga, 2012; Martínez-Carrasco, Brugarolas, Martínez-Poveda, & Ruiz-Martínez,
18 530 2015). Indeed, nonhypothetical experimental methods are becoming increasingly popular when it
19 531 comes to measuring constructs like consumer behavior (see Lim et al., 2013; & Verbeke et al., 2013;
20 532 for examples regarding the effect of package labelling on willingness to pay). Hence, further research
21 533 should aim to study whether the results of this experiment regarding consumer willingness to buy are
22 534 robust and also can be found by conducting nonhypothetical experimental methods (such as
23 535 experimental auctions, Corrigan et al., 2009, or choice experiments, Alfnes et al., 2006).

24 536 These results open the door to further research, in which it would be interesting to explicitly assess
25 537 the effect of the valence of the message to be conveyed (i.e. whether it is rendered as being positive
26 538 or negative) through different package cues on consumer expectations and response. It also might
27 539 be interesting to conduct a tasting in order to investigate what minimum amount of added sugar shall
28 540 be considered by the participants to be excessively sweet and to assess if these effects also
29 541 influence taste perception and willingness to buy. It would also be relevant to analyze in depth the
30 542 possible existence of mediation (indirect effect) of the attribute Sweet with willingness to buy through
31 543 the attribute Healthy, as the findings of this study may suggest. We believe that another interesting
32 544 line of investigation should be directed at studying how the results obtained might be affected by the
33 545 individual differences of the participants regarding health consciousness, since earlier studies
34 546 suggest that the knowledge and beliefs of the consumer influence food acceptance (Karnal,
35 547 Machiels, Orth, & Mai, 2016; Verbeke, 2005).

36 548 **5. Conclusions**

37 549 The results of this research suggest that the specific image chosen to be depicted in packaging
38 550 imagery influences consumer sensory and non-sensory expectations and willingness to buy. In
39 551 addition, these findings challenge the notion that packaging imagery improves the attitude of the
40 552 consumer towards the product, since the results of this study show that a poor image selection may

553 have a detrimental effect on consumer expectations and response than not showing any image at all.
1 554 The practical implications of these findings are of interest for both designers and producers, since
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3 555 they seem to suggest that if a product attribute that is not regarded as clearly positive by consumers
4 556 has to be conveyed in the package, it may not be a good idea to do so by depicting an image since it
5 557 may make that attribute too salient and thus negatively affect consumer expectations and willingness
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7 558 to buy. Overall, these results highlight the relevance of packaging imagery when it comes to shape
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9 559 consumer expectations and willingness to buy and imply that designers should be cautious when
10 560 deciding when to use visual cues and what to depict on them.
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807

808 **Figures and tables**

Sugar sack

Sugar cubes

Sugar spoon

Only text

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Fig. 1. Four yogurt packages were designed for this investigation, only differing in the image used to convey sweetness.

812

813 **Fig. 2.** Biplot graph of the word association task. The angle between two attributes indicates their
 814 correlation, where angles close to 0° indicate a high positive correlation, angles close to 180° indicate
 815 a high negative correlation, and angles close to 90° indicate no correlation. The orthogonal
 816 projections of the stimuli on an attribute allows to order the stimuli according to how strongly are they
 817 related to it.

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819 **Fig. 3.** Results of the one-way repeated measures analysis of variance. Means with differing letters
820 within attributes are significantly different at the p<0.05 based on Bonferroni paired comparisons.

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Fig. 4. Results of the multidimensional scaling. The angle between two attributes indicates their correlation, where angles close to 0° indicate a high positive correlation, angles close to 180° indicate a high negative correlation, and angles close to 90° indicate no correlation. The orthogonal projections of the stimuli on an attribute allows to order the stimuli according to how strongly are they related to it.

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Table 1

Means, standard deviations, and ANOVA results of the manipulation check conducted to assess the adequacy of the images chosen for this study

Attributes	Images			F (2, 100)	p	η^2
	Sugar sack M (SD)	Sugar cubes M (SD)	Sugar spoon M (SD)			
Depicted sugar quantity	5.51 (1.43) a	4.98 (1.62) a	4.00 (1.71) b	20.29	<0.001	0.29
Perceived naturalness	4.04 (1.67) a	2.92 (1.76) b	3.16 (1.59) b	13.63	<0.001	0.21

Note: Sample size N=51. Means with differing letters within rows are significantly different at the $p < 0.05$ based on Bonferroni paired comparisons.

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Table 2

Frequency of elicitations of terms for the four stimuli considered in the word association task

Category	Stimuli			
	Sugar cubes	Sugar spoon	Sugar sack	Only text
Sweet	37	17	29	11
Natural Yogurt	22	18	21	20
Nature	14	16	17	15
Cow	14	10	17	10
Milky	5	9	8	9
Healthy	2	8	7	13
Yogurt	6	8	9	6
Fresh	6	5	5	8

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Table 3

Means, standard deviations, and ANOVA results on the effect of the images depicted on the yogurt packages on consumer expectations

Attributes	Stimuli				F (3, 468)	p	η^2
	Sugar sack M (SD)	Sugar cubes M (SD)	Sugar spoon M (SD)	Only text M (SD)			
Sweet	5.09 (1.46) a	5.47 (1.47) b	5.03 (1.34) a	4.48 (1.56) c	27.53	<0.001	0.15
Healthy	4.38 (1.46) a	3.91 (1.54) b	4.20 (1.39) a	4.39 (1.59) a	10.28	<0.001	0.06
Natural Ingredients	4.22 (1.59) a	3.73 (1.56) b	3.94 (1.54) b	3.98 (1.56) ab	8.61	<0.001	0.05
Quality	4.46 (1.44) a	3.95 (1.44) b	4.25 (1.38) ac	4.20 (1.50) c	10.28	<0.001	0.06
Willingness to buy	4.48 (1.64) a	3.97 (1.69) b	4.23 (1.59) b	4.26 (1.69) ab	9.41	<0.001	0.06

Note: Sample size N=157. Means with differing letters within rows are significantly different at the $p < 0.05$ based on Bonferroni paired comparisons.

829

Figure 1
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Sugar sack

Sugar cubes

Sugar spoon

Only text

Figure 2
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 3
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 4

[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

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Note: Sample size N=157. Means with differing letters within rows are significantly different at the $p<0.05$ based on Bonferroni paired comparisons.

STIMULI

Sugar cubes

Sugar sack

Sugar spoon

Only text

RESULTS

- **Sugar cubes:** higher sweetness expectations and lower willingness to buy
- **Sugar sack:** higher naturalness expectations and higher willingness to buy
- Strong positive connection between willingness to buy, naturalness, healthfulness and quality expectations
- Strong negative connection between healthfulness and sweetness expectations